

Studies on iron-sucrose chelate formation and development of brown colour

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Formation and isolation of iron-sucrose chelate with respect to caramelization has been investigated together with the reappraisal of spectral and analytical evidences for chelate formation. The chelate was found to have salty taste but with no metallic taste. Its dark brown aqueous solution has salty, slight caramel taste but again with no metallic taste. The study suggests that the deterioration of sucrose crystal does not seem to be slow caramelisation catalysed by alkali impurities, rather it seems more likely a fast caramelisation perhaps catalysed by iron compounds naturally present in sugar crystal or compounds formed during processing of the sugar.

Interest in iron has recently received attention because of its disadvantage in catalysing the colour development¹ in sugar cane juices. Though the aspect of complex formation between iron and selected carbohydrates (glucose and fructose) has been investigated by different investigators^{2,3}, its role in catalysing the caramelisation in sugar cane juices and crystal have not been investigated. The present study reports the formation and isolation of iron-sucrose chelate with respect to brown colour development together with the reappraisal of the spectral and analytical evidences.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra (figures not shown) revealed characteristic peaks at 270–280 nm for sucrose solution (15–40%) and at 350–460 nm for ferric sulphate solutions (0.01–0.10 M). The absorption peak at 273 nm for sucrose is char-

acteristic to caramel^{1,4}. However, the complex absorption peaks at 280–350 nm were also observed for $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$. It is interesting to note that these complex peaks were masked in the spectra of the (sucrose + iron) solution mixture (Fig. 1). It illustrates the difference in spectra (as used to establish chelate formation) of sucrose, iron chelated with sucrose and free iron.

No precipitate of iron hydroxide was obtained when NaOH was added to the (sucrose + iron) solution mixture. This indicates iron-sucrose chelation. Prolonged heating (6 h) of the solution did not produce further development of colour as evidenced by the stabilisation of the absorbance after 6 h at 75° (Fig. 2). This gives indication for chelate formation as spectral changes were found to occur according to the amount of iron chelated with sucrose and when chelation was complete, its absorbance got stabilised.

Analysis of the isolated chelate : Analysis of the isolated chelate for Fe and Na was expected to give a more clear picture whether slow caramelisation caused by alkali

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of sucrose, free iron and iron-sucrose chelate.

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of sucrose and iron-sucrose chelate

Parameter	Sucrose	Iron-sucrose chelate
pH	5.00	No precipitation at 7–14
Sodium	180 ppm	300 ppm
Iron	0.98 ppm	25%
Specific rotation	+66.5	+57.3
ICUMSA colour at 420 nm	104	6533
Gustatory property	Sweet in taste	Slight caramel taste with no metallic taste

Fig. 2. Curve showing the development of brown colour in iron-sucrose solution at 75° with the progress of time : (A) 15% sucrose solution + iron and (B) 15% sucrose solution.

impurities or fast caramelisation catalysed by iron is the main factor for sugar deterioration. Physicochemical data of sucrose and sucrose-iron chelate are presented in Table 1.

At neutral pH the precipitate of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ was formed. However, when pH was lowered to 4, the precipitate remained and further lowering the pH resulted the precipitate to dissolve. The precipitate was again formed in the pH range 4–7 and no precipitate was observed in the pH range 7–14. In sucrose, the iron content was found to be 0.98 ppm, however, in chelate it was 25%. Na content in sucrose was found to be 180 ppm, whereas in chelate it was 300 ppm.

The specific rotation of the isolated chelate (+57.3) suggests the inversion (deterioration) of sucrose due to iron. Barkar *et al.*² reported similar results for iron-fructose chelate.

The gustatory properties revealed that the chelate is slightly salty having no metallic taste. The chelate dissolved in water to give a dark brown solution having a salty and slight caramel taste and again without any metallic taste.

Experimental

Chelate formation : Rectangular specimen of mild steel (composition : Fe, 99.09; C, 0.026; Si, 0.089; Mn, 0.47; P,

0.42; S, 0.042%) was used as a source of iron to chelate with sucrose. The cleaned specimen was dipped in sucrose solution (50 ml; 15%, w/v) made in double-distilled water. The content was heated at 75° in a thermostat. Development of brown colour was determined as a function of time employing a Shimadzu-260 spectrophotometer. The solution mixture of sucrose and iron obtained during the experiment was titrated from the acid pH to pH employing NaOH and formation of any precipitate was noted. The freshly prepared solutions of sucrose and iron were also mixed in pre-determined proportions and titrated as above.

Isolation of the chelate : To the dark brown iron-sucrose chelate that remained for 6 h at 75°, was added 2.0 M NaOH solution (50 ml) and its pH maintained at 8.5–9.0. To it absolute ethanol was added to 50% by volume and the resulting brown solid was dissolved in distilled water (50 ml) and re-precipitation was carried out. The creamy brown-yellow mass was dried over P_2O_5 .

Iron content was determined spectrophotometrically at 510 nm employing 1,10-phenanthroline method⁵. Sodium content was determined using a flame photometer. The detailed method is described elsewhere⁶.

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